

Altruism In The Verb Type In The Book Manhat Al-Bari, Explained By Sahih Al-Bukhari Al-Siniki (D. 926 AH)

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Abstract

We thought that we should study altruism in action in the book Manhat al-Bari al-Siniki, given the importance of the subject and the extent of its influence in determining the meaning. Two words may share one meaning, but one of them is more accurate than the other in denoting the meaning, and the other is more capable of expressing it than the other. It performs the intended meaning in the most accurate and fulfilling manner, without the role of other words. The prophetic expression is distinguished in the choice of words, as it is elegant in its choice and places it in the position in which it accurately performs its meaning. It is comparable to the Qur'anic expression in that. He placed each word according to the context and chose the appropriate place for it. Preferring verbs means choosing and giving preference to a particular act over another for an intended rhetorical joke, and the point of it is to achieve a meaning required by the context.

Introduction

As it is well known that the Arabic verbs are three: past, present and imperative. These verbs have a connotation, as the past verb indicates a past and past time, and the present tense indicates the time of the present and the reception, while the imperative verb indicates the reception, but each of these verbs may take the place of the other, for an expressive reason and a rhetorical joke required by the context and the place. Ibn al-Shajari said: ((The Arabs have placed some examples of verbs in the position of some, with the knowledge of what they mean, so they put the past in the position of the future, and the future in the position of the past...)). It includes the saying of the Most High: {Why did you not kill the prophets of God before?} [Al-Baqarah: from verse: 91].

This was mentioned a lot in the words of the Prophet, peace be upon him, as it came in his words that contradict the apparent requirement to express the alternation of verbs among them; The commentators did not neglect the talk about that, but they warned him, and they separated the words about it.

Altruism is divided into two sections.

The first topic

Preposition of the past tense in the present tense

The past tense may be used in the present or in the future; For purposes required by the context, including:

-Told:

About Anas Bin Malik: The Messenger of Allah ﷺ came out when the sun Zagat came back after the back, and he said on the platform, he mentioned the hour. This is my place."⁽³⁾ Al-Sunqi said, explaining: "**I told you**," i.e., ((I told you about it, so I put the past into the place of the future, indicating that it is like reality in order to achieve it)). That the question of the Prophet, peace be upon him, in the past tense, which occurred in the present tense verb, is a sign of his realization, and that it is like the reality, and it is close to the Almighty's saying: {And on the day when the images are blown, then fear those in the heavens and those in the earth} [Al-Naml: Verse 87]. For he only said: "So he was terrified," in the past tense, to indicate the realization of panic, and that it will inevitably exist. He told him about the future verb that did not exist yet.

- Entered:

The Prophet, peace and blessings be upon him, said: ((He who prays Al-Bardayn will enter Paradise)). Al-Sunqi said explaining: ((So he came with "entered" without "entering"; because the event is certain, like the reality)). The commentators of the hadith mentioned that Al-Bardan: means Fajr and Asr prayers, and that the past tense verb "entered" came, and the context requires the present tense "to enter"; This is either because he established the past in place of the future; In order to confirm its occurrence, and make it as reality, And the same is the saying of the Most High: {And he will call out to the companions of Paradise} [Al-A'raf: from verse 44], and the Almighty's saying: {And they all stand out before God} [Ibrahim: from verse 21].), or because the inclusion

of “who” is the meaning of the condition, and the past is made after it in the sense of the future. The condition, including: “who”, whose ruling is the rule of “if”. Ibn al-Hajib said: ((The correct thing is that the conditional, if you enter into the past, turns it into the future)). And as Ibn Malik mentioned that the tools of the condition, including: “who” are ruled by the rule of “if”. The context of the conversation requires the two stakeholders; According to the first meaning, he wanted to confirm the entry into Paradise for the one who prayed Fajr and Asr, so he crossed the past verb indicative of the occurrence the verb that has not yet been signed, and on the second meaning, "who" has included the meaning of the condition, and the past in the condition and its answer is in the sense of the future.

The second topic

Present tense in the past tense

It is to use the present tense to express the past for the purpose of clarifying the form of the verb and evoking its image, so that the listener is as if he is witnessing it, as Ibn Hisham said: ((They express the past and the future as they express the present thing with the intention of bringing it into the mind until it was scenes of the state of the news))

Like the saying of the Most High: {And it is God who sends the winds, and they raise clouds} [Fatir: from verse 9]. The Almighty did not say: (Then they affected) in the past tense, but rather the present tense (they provoke) to evoke the wonderful image that indicates the dazzling power of stirring clouds, as if it were happening now. As they appear first as scattered pieces, then they combine and overlap among themselves until they become rubble, and water is formed from them. Among the places where al-Sunqi cautioned in “Minhat al-Bari” to give preference to the present tense are:

-See:

The Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: ((While I was sleeping, I was brought a mug of milk, and I drank until I saw water coming out of my nails, Then I gave the rest to Omar Bin Al-Khattab)), They said: What did you interpret, O Messenger of God? He said: ((Science)) Al-Sunaiki explained: ((to see” by opening the hamza, and he mentioned the present tense, to bring up this vision for the listeners))

Some commentators pointed out that the altruism in “I see” over “He sees” came to evoke the image of the vision for the listeners; In order to inform them of the event when it occurred. Since the context requires invoking the occurrence of the event, the present tense is brought up in two places in this hadith, the first place in the verb “I see,” and the other in the verb “exit,” and this is close to the Almighty’s saying: [Al-Baqarah: From verse 91], Dr. Fadel Al-Samarrai said, commenting on the verse: ((The killing happened in the past. Do you not see his saying: “before”), but it was expressed by the action of Al-Da’ari, in reference to this heinous image of killing God’s prophets, so he took off the scene the image of life movement by making it present in front of the seer’s eye.

-Know:

The Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, said((If people know what is in the appeal and the first line, then they have only been forced to contribute to them, even if they know what to retain, even if they know what is in the darkness and the morning for them, even if they crawling), Al-Sunqi said, explaining: ((“If people knew,” putting the present in the place of the past, to benefit the continuation of knowledge)).

He should have said: "If the people knew" because the conditional "if" is often followed by the past tense.

But the present tense verb comes after it in this place. To give meaning that the context requires which is: Continuation, as the Korani said: ((If you say: “If” is to interfere with the past, then why did he choose the present? I said: It indicates the continuity of knowledge, and that the matter is something that should be taken care of.”)). Or bring a picture what is related to this strange matter that necessitates keenness to achieve it and win it to the point of defeating it. Al-Tibi said: ((This means; if he knew, then he brought the present tense to establish a place for him that calls for him, since what is meant: then they tried to anticipate it because it is obligatory for them to do so, or to benefit the continuity of knowledge, and that it should be on the mind)). The noble Prophetic hadith does not contradict the two meanings, as it indicates the greatness of the call, and the first line came with the present tense verb to indicate continuing to maintain this, or to evoke the image.

Conclusion

After God's grace and generosity granted me, I completed this research, and reached the most beautiful results as follows:

1. Altruism is not limited to one type of verbs, but includes all of them in the past and present, and the same applies to the action of the command (imperative).
2. The Prophet, may God’s prayers and peace be upon him, preferred to act in the place of the other in order to achieve rhetorical purposes, the most important of which is to tighten the mind of the addressee and listen to him, or because of the importance of the matter or its continuation.
3. Use the present tense to express the past for the purpose of clarifying the form of the verb and evoking its image, so that the listener is as if he is watching it.

4. Context had a prominent role in determining the use of the verb type.

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